

Hand Puttying 14,416 Panes of Glass

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The Britannia Mine Museum is a National Historic Site that lies about 50 km north of Vancouver in British Columbia. The Museum is governed by the Britannia Beach Historical Society and operates as a tourist attraction which sees around 60,000 visitors and 10,000 students a year exploring the history of the former Britannia Mine while learning about the relevance of mining and minerals in our daily lives. In the Museum's care are twenty two heritage buildings, around 7000 artefacts, 3000 archival documents and 9500 archive photos. The Museum opened in 1975 and has been delivering underground guided tours alongside exhibits since then.

Former Britannia Mine

The Britannia Mine was a copper mine which ran from 1904 to 1974. An isolated company town, it was reportedly home to more than 60,000 people from over 50 nationalities over its life. The mine was situated on a natural deep harbour, along the shores of Howe Sound. This is a fjord that ultimately leads to the Pacific Ocean, and so although isolated, the mine was well placed to export its ore to smelters abroad, as well as importing goods and people via steamship. In fact for many years the mine was a customs port of entry into Canada. Despite its proximity to Vancouver, the mine was only connected to the outside world via rail and road from 1956 and 1958 respectively.

There were two townsites and several camps. Mining occurred at and around Mount Sheer, 4.5 km inland and at an elevation of around 600 metres. Processing of ore occurred at Britannia Beach in a gravity fed concentrator, or mill building. Using the steep mountainside to advantage, ore was brought in by locomotive to the top of the building before going through a series of crushers and grinders, often propelled by gravity, until it was the consistency of fine sand. It then went through a process called froth flotation which is a technique used to separate valuable minerals from waste rock.

In all there were three mills at 'The Beach' – Mill 1, 2 and finally 3. Mill 1 was demolished when too small for operations. Mill 2 was destroyed by fire in 1921 and Mill 3 was constructed as quickly as possible after the loss of Mill 2.

Mill 3 Significance

Mill 3 was built over a period of 18 months between 1921 and 1923 at a cost of \$1 million. Built from concrete and steel it was an architectural feat of engineering and it was reported that engineers came from all over to visit it.

Mill 3 is described as the heartbeat of the community. At twenty-six storeys high it dominated the town. Dusty and noisy there was no escaping it. Yet a quiet Mill meant that no ore was being processed, which meant less ore to sell. As this was a company town, every resident had a vested interest in as much ore being sold as possible. One former resident described “crying her eyes out” when the Mill went silent for the last time in 1974 for she knew it signaled the end.

Being the processing plant, the Mill was largely responsible for the success of the Mine. With no money to be made from shipping out waste rock, it was imperative that the Mine process the ore as efficiently as possible. And this they did to exceptional ability. They developed a system known as the ‘deep cell’ system that allowed them to extract upwards of 95% of the ore, which for its time was very high.

At the Mine’s peak in the early 1930s, the Mill was processing up to 7000 tons of rock per day. This accounted for the mine producing 17% of the world’s copper and becoming the largest copper mine in the then British Empire. The Mill also processed for zinc, lead, gold, silver and cadmium.

It is Mill 3 that is primarily responsible for the 1987 National Historic Site designation, for its contribution to the Canadian economy and its innovative use of froth flotation. Today it is last remaining gravity fed mill in Canada.

Mill 3 Degradation

As might be expected, while the mine was operational, the Mill was well maintained. Highly innovative, the Company made many changes to the interior in order to enhance efficiency, but the exterior remained relatively unchanged for over fifty years.

Only after mine closure did time start to take its toll. Britannia Beach lies in BC’s coastal temperate rainforest. Winters are wet and summers are warm. Being on the coast, the town is frequently buffeted by strong winds. As a result, with no maintenance, since 1974 the building began to deteriorate.

Safety and security in the building was hard to maintain. It had been a spot for local teens to hang out in at night for three decades and was also an area that the Museum wanted to be able to confidently take visitors into. The state of the building was therefore a significant risk management issue.

Rehabilitation

A motion from the Board to demolish the building had actually been taken, however this was going to cost about \$1 million. But the stars aligned and the possibility of \$2 million of a government infrastructure grant as well as the desire to upgrade the Museum in time for the newly announced 2010 Winter Olympic Games in Whistler prompted the change in direction to rehabilitate the building. At this time, the mine site as a whole was undergoing remediation and a developer was beginning investment of significant dollars into the rest of the community. And so the rehabilitation of the Mill became a linchpin in this overall revitalization project.

By the fall of 2005, \$3 million was secured from federal and provincial governments along with industry and private donors. It quickly became apparent though that this would not be enough. The project was in danger of not proceeding, however a further \$2 million was secured allowing the project to go ahead.

Despite the overall \$5 million budget it was decided that to keep costs down and to aim to meet the project timeline, the Museum would take ownership of the window refurbishment. To reach this stage though the Museum still had to go through a competitive bid process in order to convince the project management company that it was viable as well as meeting the requirements of the government grant.

Windows Project

The windows were deemed to be the most significant architectural and heritage feature of the building. They were all double hung and single glazed sash windows, each around 4 x 9 feet. Each contained, or was supposed to contain, thirty two individual panes of glass. With 901 windows to repair or manufacture in only six months (including the time it took to set up shop and place orders), this project would be no easy task. The Museum's Site Manager knew it could be done though.

Although almost ninety years old, the old growth Douglas Fir used in the windows' original construction had clearly been a factor in their longevity. The condition assessment of the windows revealed that about 50 - 60% of sashes were considered salvageable. The window frames (jambs, headrails, sills and mullions) were in good condition on the front of the building meaning that most did not have to be removed. The sashes on this face were mostly able to be reconditioned. The frames and sashes however facing the prevailing wind direction were all in poor condition and had to be replaced. The frames were manufactured by an outside firm and the sashes were manufactured in house.

A contractor was used to remove the window sashes, along with the frames that were being replaced. They also applied preservative to the frames that were being kept. Once the sashes were delivered to the in house crew the refurbishment work could begin.

Sash Refurbishment

The first stage of refurbishing the sashes was to remove the old putty and glass, with the latter being recycled. The windows were then power washed. A number of the muntins had to be replaced. Where possible these were done using parts from the windows which were not salvageable. After the woodwork had been complete, the windows were treated with preservative and painted.

The glazing was done with all new glass using double panes laminated together. This was in order to strengthen the glass, giving them longevity. Once fitted, each pane was hand puttied in place. The glass was cleaned and the window was ready for reinstallation by the contractor. This work was done in three months.

For the manufacture of the new windows, it was a more involved process. Suitable equipment was purchased including having the muntin profile made for the router. The crew worked in pairs on an assembly line and used the old windows as a pattern. Components were hand assembled using mortice and tenon joinery, though they were also glued and pinned to hold in place and give strength. Each new sash was then treated with preservative, primed and then painted ready for glazing and puttying.

Old growth fir was used for this project. This was not a decision to be taken lightly owing to the ethical values in harvesting old growth wood. However, as the use of old growth fir in the original windows was a testament to their longevity, it was argued that to help ensure the new windows were also able to withstand another century, then old growth should again be used.

Ultimately, over 70% of windows were salvaged. In all, 650 original windows were saved and 251 new windows manufactured. This totalled 14,416 panes of glass hand putted in – that is 57,664 edges to putty. This in house windows project cost \$250,000. This saved around \$500,000 on the other quotes that were received during the bidding process for the project.

Siding and Roofing

The rest of the rehabilitation project involved securing the building's concrete foundations, improving its structural integrity and replacing exterior materials with new cladding and roofing. The existing cladding was generally left intact as it added character to the interior of the building as well as helping to tell the story of the building and its rehabilitation. To save some cost, one side of the building, which had previously had the windows boarded up, was again cladded over.

Although unable to install a water capture system owing to budget limitations, water is now channeled along the edge of each roof to discharge sideways off the building; as opposed to previously where rainwater cascaded down over each roof to the ground. Snow stops have also since been installed.

In House Crew

A fifteen strong crew of men and women worked on the windows project. As a group of untested non-professional wood workers, this was a gamble but was thankfully one that paid off. Several were residents of Britannia Beach and had a vested interest in the successful completion of the project. In addition, the Museum hired men from the local community of Squamish who had recently been laid off from careers at BC Rail. These were men who were mechanically and technically skilled. They were also a close knit group and did not want to leave the area to look for work. And so the in house crew became a dedicated group who were proud to be working on this project. In addition, with the oversight of the Museum's Site Manager as in house project manager, and Crew Foreman, the team was led well and guided in quality control.

Heritage Values

In 1999, Parks Canada completed a full condition report on the building. This, plus an engineering report reviewed the building components suitable for saving. Owing to the scale and cost of the project, a conservation plan that Parks Canada had recommended could not be implemented. As a result this was classed as a rehabilitation project, i.e. making possible a continuing or compatible contemporary use through repair, alterations and/or additions, while protecting its heritage value. The Board however did choose the highest quality of the tender options in order to ensure the longevity and legacy of the building.

The cladding and roofing was replaced, not repaired, though as the existing cladding was left intact beneath the new skin, this has preserved some of the original materials.

With the 650 salvaged windows, this part of the project saw the greatest ability to restore and repair. The Museum drew on Parks Canada's conservation experience in preservative, sealer and paint applications and was able to apply most of these standards to the windows project.

The puttying of the windows was also taught by professional glazier, who also came back to check on quality control.

Project Risks

The overall project came with much risk. With no 'How-to-Restore-a-26-Storey-Gravity-Fed-Mill' manual to work from, there were many unknowns going into the project. This led to the risk that it could not be done on time or on budget and the Museum's Board were very conscious of this. Project management was outsourced to AMEC, being a world class project management firm, in order to maximize the likelihood of success.

For a Museum of its size (about 12 permanent staff at the time), the Windows Project was by far the biggest project to date. A good and flexible working relationship with AMEC was essential, but not yet formed. It is to the testament of the firm and to the Museum's Site Manager that this proceeded well.

Despite the \$5 million investment, funds also still had to be raised for the Windows Project. The Museum launched a fundraising effort – Windows on Howe Sound – which managed to raise \$110,000 from 350 contributors.

Despite the risks, the entire rehabilitation project, taking eighteen months to complete (October 2005 to April 2007), came in on time and on budget. It is interesting to note that this is the timeframe in which the entire building was constructed in the 1920s.

Project Benefits

By keeping the Windows Project in house, the benefits are several. One, jobs were created for a community that was in need of a boost to employment. Secondly, it saved the project component almost \$500,000 – compared to the cost of outsourcing to an external firm. It also allowed the Museum to control and adhere to as many Parks Canada restoration standards as possible.

Perhaps most importantly, the project has given the Museum invaluable experience in restoration and rehabilitation projects, of which the Mill became only the first. Some of the windows crew stayed on at the Museum, working on further projects. Since 2007 a further five buildings have been preserved, restored or rehabilitated for adaptive reuse – mostly grant funded, with a further three buildings receiving interior rehabilitation treatment. Each project builds on the experience gained. Those of the crew that stayed became important to the journey of heritage preservation, helping to pass on the knowledge to new maintenance and project staff. It is also fair to say that had the Museum been forced to contract out any restoration work, it would have been cost prohibitive, even with grant funding.

Conclusion

Both the Windows Project and the overall rehabilitation project has been a major catalyst for the Museum. It has given staff the belief that “we can do anything” as well as confidence in the ability to manage large capital projects despite time constraints and the need at times for quick decision making. It has also given the Board a major hook in which to hang its fundraising hat – a further \$10 million has been raised and spent on redevelopment since then.

Before and after photos for context:

